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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This deliverable is a collection of policy insights gathered during the course of the GREAT project. It includes five policy related documents. Two policy briefs cover specific insights from some of the GREAT case studies and are primarily dedicated towards national policy makers, while the other three documents summarise recommendations at a broader level and across case studies.
Keywords	policy brief, game-based approaches, society-policy engagement
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List of Abbreviations

CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DiBL	Dilemma-based Learning Game (a product of the GREAT partner Serious Games Interactive)
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PV	Photovoltaic
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme

Executive Summary

The GREAT (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation) project investigates how games can meaningfully contribute to citizen engagement and dialogue with policymakers, particularly in the context of climate change. The project's approach rests on the premise that games, as a pervasive and culturally dominant medium, can serve not only as tools for learning but also as innovative platforms for public consultation and policy co-design. Supported by the Horizon Europe programme and UK Research and Innovation, it deploys both in-depth qualitative methods and large-scale public engagement exercises to test how interactive gameplay might open new channels of communication between citizens and decision-makers.

The first of the five policy briefs presented in this compendium outlines the foundational insights of the project, which has conducted a series of game-based case studies across diverse national contexts. This policy brief was the first strategic document elaborated at a time when the project was relying on a limited number of pilot cases. Thus, it was based on limited empirical evidence, but nonetheless it served as an important insights document for the further development of case studies. As the brief outlines, two principal methods were employed in GREAT: moderated dilemma-based games that support qualitative participation in small groups, and large-scale collaborations with commercial digital games in which player responses to embedded questions offer insights at scale. An example of the first method is seen in Austria, where a serious game involving young adults provided actionable insights on motivating uptake of green jobs. The second method is exemplified by a collaboration with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), where climate-related survey questions were integrated into the game *SMITE*, reaching nearly 3,000 participants worldwide. Across these trials, the project has confirmed both the appetite for and effectiveness of game-based policy consultation, while highlighting critical factors such as the need for clearly defined policy questions, appropriate incentives for citizens, and close cooperation between researchers and public institutions.

The second document, the “Gaming for Good” whitepaper, adds further perspective by exploring how the commercial gaming industry can actively contribute to climate action. It is the outcome of the *Gaming for Good* roundtable, hosted during the 2024 Sustainability Summit in New York City, which brought together gaming executives, environmental advocates, and policymakers to explore how gaming can play a pivotal role in driving climate action. With over 3 billion players and annual revenues exceeding \$200 billion, the gaming sector represents a uniquely powerful cultural and

economic force. The report argues that gaming could drive behavioural change on environmental issues by embedding climate-conscious stories, reward systems, and missions directly into gameplay. Initiatives such as sustainability-themed challenges, interoperable “impact score” systems, and cross-platform incentives are highlighted as mechanisms through which individual players could be motivated to adopt environmentally positive behaviours. Beyond content development, the report also points to the need for regulatory innovation, such as tax incentives or transparency rules for energy use and carbon footprint reporting. These recommendations reflect a broader push for deeper collaboration between the gaming industry, policymakers, and environmental organisations to embed sustainability into game design, production, and consumption practices.

The third document, a detailed insight report from Cyprus, illustrates how game-based tools can support localised policymaking processes. The “Rooftops Reimagined” project uses a serious dilemma game to explore the potential and policy challenges of implementing green roofs in urban Cyprus. Through five structured game sessions involving citizens, architects, and students, the study generated a rich body of evidence regarding the public’s perceptions of green roof benefits, barriers to adoption, and preferred policy approaches. Participants consistently identified benefits such as improved air quality, enhanced urban biodiversity, energy savings, and the creation of new social and recreational spaces. At the same time, they highlighted major barriers including financial constraints, structural safety concerns, and the need for maintenance and clear governance in multi-residential buildings. The study’s policy recommendations emphasise the importance of establishing clear communication frameworks between residents and building managers, providing evidence-based financial incentives, ensuring equitable access to benefits, and building professional capacity through targeted training. These insights underscore the value of participatory mechanisms not only for gathering data but also for building public awareness, fostering local ownership, and supporting inclusive urban planning.

The fourth document (in German) emerged from the Green Jobs case study, a dilemma-based role-play exercise conducted in Austrian schools. The aim was to understand which factors influence young people’s career choices and how climate-related professions could become more attractive to a wider and more diverse youth population. The analysis indicates that students prioritise financial stability, personal interest, fulfilment, and work–life balance when considering future occupations. Security and long-term prospects remain central. These factors also shape attitudes towards climate-related jobs. The discussions reveal that students consider climate-related careers

viable only if they offer competitive salaries, flexibility, and clear advancement opportunities. Recommended interventions for raising interest in green jobs include paid internships and well-structured trial days, provided they allow freedom of choice. Communication strategies should rely on contemporary social media platforms such as TikTok, with a preference for positive narratives over images emphasising harm or crisis. Financial incentives, including tax reductions and free public transport for workers in climate-related occupations, also emerged as motivating factors. Gender-sensitive communication requires better visibility of women and non-binary people working in climate-related fields alongside opportunities to present diverse role models and counteract traditional occupational images. Additional reflections from the role-play discussions emphasise the need to strengthen the societal recognition of climate-related jobs. Students suggested that public campaigns should communicate climate professions as meaningful contributions to mitigation and sustainability, supported by real-world success stories to illustrate tangible impacts. They also called for realistic portrayals of job tasks, acknowledging both opportunities and constraints. While many were open to climate-related careers, some felt uncertain and wished to learn more about alternative pathways. More extensive preparation for the role-play scenario and opportunities to experiment with different decision-making roles were also requested. Overall, the findings suggest that young people respond positively to creative engagement formats and value autonomy, realism, and clear societal appreciation. Designing programmes that highlight the meaningfulness, diversity, and accessibility of climate-related jobs—while also addressing financial and structural concerns—would support efforts to engage a broader and more diverse group of young people in green careers.

The fifth and final policy brief summarizes contributions from policymakers, academics, game developers, UN agencies, investors, and civil society organisations at a workshop held in New York at the last quarter of the GREAT project. Drawing on this multi-stakeholder workshop, it shows that games can act as a bridge between citizens and institutions, a parallel public sphere for cross-border dialogue, and a highly scalable mechanism for gathering qualitative and quantitative insights on public attitudes. Through co-designed, ethically grounded methodologies, GREAT demonstrates how dilemma-based serious games and large-scale in-game prompts can elicit meaningful citizen input, particularly on sustainability and climate change, from audiences that are often difficult to reach through conventional consultation methods. Participants consistently engage when approached respectfully, offered agency, and invited to express their views rather than be instructed or persuaded.

The brief also highlights a critical challenge: translating large-scale player input into tangible policy impact. Key gaps include unclear policy objectives, limited capacity within policymaking institutions to interpret game-generated data, and weak feedback loops that erode trust when participants do not see outcomes. To address this, the brief recommends aligning game-based engagement with formal policy processes, working with policy intermediaries, combining small-scale deliberative games with mass participation, and treating engagement as an iterative dialogue rather than a one-off consultation. It further emphasises the importance of designing sustainability content that avoids fatigue, fosters hope and agency, and integrates seamlessly into gameplay, alongside the emerging potential of extended reality to deepen empathy and understanding. Overall, the brief concludes that games can function as critical civic infrastructures, but only if their use is intentional, collaborative, and clearly connected to policy pathways.

Taken together, these five briefs reveal the versatile and scalable potential of games as mechanisms for climate engagement and policy innovation. Whether soliciting public input through community-focused simulations, reaching global audiences through commercial game integration, or facilitating policy discussion among stakeholders, games provide uniquely interactive frameworks for participatory governance. They enable citizens to explore complex issues, adopt the perspectives of others, and contribute directly to the development of policy solutions. The GREAT project's approach demonstrates that digital play can be a substantive channel for robust citizen consultation and collaborative policymaking. The findings across these briefs point to the opportunity for policymakers, game developers, and civil society actors to work more systematically together, leveraging the engaging, reflective, and scalable nature of games to transform both environmental governance and democratic participation.

Introduction

This compendium brings together five policy briefs produced within the framework of the GREAT (Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation) project, an international research initiative exploring the potential of gaming to foster public engagement and enhance dialogue between citizens and policymakers on pressing societal issues. Each brief reflects a distinct dimension of this work: 1) the adoption of game-based methods to surface citizen perspectives and inform policy design; 2) the evolving role of the global gaming industry in advancing environmental sustainability; and 3) in-depth case studies demonstrating how interactive dilemma

games can support policy innovation in areas such as urban green infrastructure or green jobs for youth.

Together, the five documents offer complementary insights into how game-based tools and participatory design can be leveraged to support inclusive, data-driven policymaking in the context of climate change and sustainable development. This collection is intended as a resource for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders committed to harnessing digital culture for transformative civic and environmental action. They have been strategically distributed to stakeholders and are available on Zenodo (see references at the end of the document), where they have already reached around 1.000 views in total.

Policy Briefs

Original policy briefs attached as Annexes

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Policy Insight Briefing

Executive Summary

This policy brief, the inaugural edition from the GREAT project, introduces initial insights from two innovative approaches aimed at leveraging games to promote social engagement and facilitate dialogue between citizens and policymakers. The GREAT project, in collaboration with global and national stakeholders like the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Urban Gorillas Cyprus, or the Austrian Klimafonds is conducting a series of case studies focused on climate change.

Introduction

The GREAT (Games Realising Effective & Affective Transformation) Project explores the potential of games to foster social engagement and enhance dialogue between citizens and policymakers. A programme of practical case studies is underway, fostering citizen engagement and in the democratic process, with a focus on climate change policy priorities. Games culture is ubiquitous, and games are now this preeminent entertainment media globally, but their potential for interaction between citizens and policymakers has not yet been explored. The GREAT case studies leverage innovative engagement strategies to investigate how games-based activities can enable citizens to express their views on social and policy dilemmas. This initiative is supported by UK Research and Innovation and the EU's Horizon Europe program.

Methods

GREAT deploys technologies and methodologies that create new communication channels between citizens and policymakers, generating actionable insights for policy makers while respecting ethics and data privacy. This is achieved through co-designed, scalable interventions tested in real-world conditions, engaging audiences that can be difficult to reach using more established methodologies.

Two principal approaches are investigated:

- Firstly, dilemma-based serious games are used to generate in-depth qualitative insights from a relatively small, moderated group of participants.
- Secondly, questions for players are embedded in high profile games, enabling quantitative data to be obtained from very large numbers of respondents, who can be engaged at global, national or district level.

Throughout the project, we employ participatory methods, involving key audiences, including policy stakeholders, in the design, prototyping, and research phases.

Authentic input, interaction, and collaboration are crucial, with continuous feedback and optimization. With our citizen science approach, we go beyond mere consultation, uncovering implicit knowledge through varying degrees of participation, from consultation to empowerment.

While the focus of GREAT is on the global challenges of sustainability and climate change the project methodologies are both scalable and transferable to other issues.

Example case: Green jobs

In Austria, schools were invited to implement a dilemma game on the issues of green jobs for young adults aged 15+. During a two-hour moderated intervention, students were asked to step into the role of policy agents and create a communication strategy to motivate young people to choose a career in green jobs. In addition, the communication should pay attention to gender inclusiveness. Results were discussed with a climate agency responsible for implementing such a strategy. With the insights from the dilemma game, they were able to identify additional motivational factors and launched a communication strategy on green jobs for schools.

Example case: UNDP

In an exploratory case study, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and GREAT partners explored methods and approaches to engage the global community in climate change policy discussions.

A set of questions to engage players in the climate change debate were posted to global players of the game SMITE, a free to play third person Multiplayer Online Battle Arena digital game, between December 2023 and March 2024. With the results from almost 3.000 engaged global players, UNDP is entering the next phase of consultation and is developing their approach for further including climate topics in online games.

Insights for policy dialogue

The GREAT project research case studies provide several insights for policy development, participatory engagement, and dialogue about climate change.

There is great potential for participatory engagement to enhance the development of game-based tools for climate change.

The potential of game-based approaches for engagement in climate action is confirmed. Two levels of dialogue are identified:

- As direct interactions, for example in conversations between stakeholders during case study activities that include co-design and data interpretation.
- As exchanges of information between policy makers and citizens, mediated by game-based activities.

It is important that policy stakeholders (1) have clearly defined needs for public consultation, or willingness to collaborate in identifying them, and (2) are available to participate in designing and interpreting the intervention.

For participatory actions requiring efforts from citizens, compensations should be considered; there is a risk of imbalance if researchers and policy makers are acting during their paid working hours while citizens would be expected to participate on a voluntary basis.

Transforming participants' concerns into the game-based approach was difficult with limited commitment from the policy stakeholder side and the citizens.

Managing expectations and timing is crucial and should be negotiated right at the beginning of the proposed activities.

Large numbers of players can be reached by collaborating with large-scale successful commercial games.

Both the large-scale embedding of questions in commercial games, and intensive interactions in moderated dilemma games offer opportunities for consultation, collaboration and co-creation with stakeholders.

There is a risk of researchers biases or expectations conditioning the results, which can be addressed by strong collaboration from participants in the inquiry.

Data sprints can be very valuable instruments to engage with citizens on relevant aspects. They can be conversation openers that help to trigger interesting discussions on specific data sets or research results. However, this requires thorough preparation and visualization to be effective.

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Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Further information

Partners

DIPF Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education, Germany

Serious Games Interactive, Denmark

Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Austria

Universidad Internacional de la Rioja, Spain

Frederick University, Cyprus

University of Bolton, England

Sphaira Innovation Ltd (PlanetPlay), England

Associate Partners

Northwest University, South Africa

Beijing Normal University, China

Project details	Publications
<p>https://www.greatproject.gg/</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/communities/101094766/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest</p>

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GAMING FOR GOOD

Harnessing the power of gaming to advance the sustainability agenda.

Dr. Barbara Kieslinger, ZSI
Mathias Gredal Nørvig, SYBO
Jude Ower, PlanetPlay

Executive summary

The gaming industry, with over 3 billion players globally and annual revenues surpassing \$200 billion, stands as a cultural and economic juggernaut. With its unmatched reach, technological innovation, and highly engaged audience, the gaming sector offers unique opportunities to address pressing global challenges such as climate change. The Gaming for Good roundtable, hosted during the 2024 Sustainability Summit in New York City, brought together gaming executives, environmental advocates, and policy-makers to explore how gaming can play a pivotal role in driving climate action. This whitepaper presents the key insights from the roundtable, highlights opportunities, and outlines actionable recommendations for stakeholders across the gaming ecosystem to advance sustainability efforts.

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this document are solely those of the authors and participants and do not necessarily reflect the opinions or official stance of the organisations.

Participating partners

Introduction

The world is at a critical juncture, with the impacts of climate change becoming increasingly severe and widespread. Addressing this crisis requires unprecedented collaboration and innovation across all sectors, including the gaming industry. As gaming platforms continue to grow in influence, they can be leveraged to promote sustainability, foster environmental awareness, and catalyze behavioral change. The Gaming for Good roundtable explored these themes, emphasizing the potential of games to serve as platforms for climate advocacy and action. This whitepaper consolidates the discussions and outcomes from that roundtable, offering a roadmap for stakeholders to align their efforts in advancing sustainability through gaming.

The Role of Gaming in the Sustainability Agenda

Global Reach and Immersive Engagement

Gaming is uniquely positioned to engage a vast and diverse audience on environmental issues. Through interactive and immersive experiences, games can communicate complex sustainability challenges in ways that resonate with players on an emotional and intellectual level. Games can also influence behavior, encouraging players to adopt eco-friendly practices both in-game and in their daily lives.

Building a Climate-Conscious Gaming Culture

The gaming industry has already taken steps to incorporate sustainability themes into its content. Initiatives like the Playing for the Planet Alliance have shown how gaming companies can integrate climate messages into their games, fostering awareness and driving real-world action. However, there is a need for more comprehensive efforts to embed sustainability across the entire gaming ecosystem—from game design and development to community engagement and corporate practices.

Strategic Opportunities for Stakeholders

This section outlines actionable recommendations for game developers, publishers, policy-makers, environmental organizations, and gaming communities. These actions are designed to maximize the gaming industry's potential to drive the sustainability agenda forward.

1. Game Developers and Publishers

a. Integrating Sustainability into Game Design

Recommendation: Game developers should incorporate sustainability themes, missions, and challenges within games to subtly educate players about environmental issues without compromising entertainment value. By creating interactive storylines that reflect real-world environmental challenges, games can influence players' perceptions and encourage eco-conscious behaviors.

- **Example:** Games like *Subway Surfers* or *Minecraft* offer players the chance to engage with sustainability issues through resource management and environmental stewardship. These mechanics should be expanded and replicated across other genres.

Recommendation: Develop or join in-game reward systems that incentivize climate-positive behaviors. These rewards could be tied to actions such as reducing energy consumption, recycling, or participating in conservation efforts.

- **Action Point:** Introduce cross-platform challenges where players earn unique in-game items or avatars based on completing sustainability-related tasks, such as recycling or reducing energy usage in-game and in real life. Make use of generative AI to guide players toward eco-conscious decisions.
- **Example:** One Earth Rising and VeChain are introducing a cross-game, cross-platform “Impact Score” system. Participating in real-life conservation efforts or playing games with embedded social impact features can increase a player’s global “Impact Score” displayed in their user account. This Impact Score system gamifies social impact, allowing gamers to earn interoperable in-game characters that drive awareness of social causes. In essence, this creates a way for gamers to earn “social bragging rights” based on their involvement in making a positive impact.

b. Promoting Cross-Platform Sustainability Initiatives

Recommendation: Establish a “green badge” certification system to recognize games that incorporate sustainability themes effectively. This certification should be visible across gaming platforms, allowing players to easily identify and support climate-conscious games.

- **Action Point:** Work with platform holders (e.g., PlayStation, Xbox, Steam) to create a top-rated sustainability leaderboard that showcases games making meaningful contributions to the sustainability agenda.

Recommendation: Create systems that allow players to earn eco-friendly in-game items by completing sustainability challenges in multiple games, fostering collaboration and promoting sustainable actions.

- **Action Point:** Develop daily or weekly challenges across multiple titles that reward players for completing outdoor or eco-friendly activities, such as visiting parks or engaging in conservation efforts.

c. Incentivizing Corporate Partnerships

Recommendation: Collaborate with corporate sponsors from outside the gaming industry to create green-themed events and challenges within games. These partnerships can drive corporate social responsibility (CSR) while offering players meaningful ways to contribute to high-integrity environmental causes.

- **Action Point:** Encourage companies to sponsor sustainability-themed events, such as reforestation or plastic waste reduction, where players’ in-game actions translate into real-world benefits.

2. Policymakers and Regulators

a. Incentivizing Sustainable Game Development

Recommendation: Governments should offer financial incentives, such as tax breaks or grants, to game developers that integrate climate-conscious themes or reduce their environmental footprint.

- **Action Point:** Create frameworks that reward developers for energy-efficient coding practices and the development of games that promote climate advocacy.

Recommendation: Establish regulatory mechanisms that promote transparency around the carbon footprint of gaming infrastructure. Governments should work with gaming companies to set sustainability benchmarks for game development, data centers, and platform usage.

- **Action Point:** Implement energy-efficiency standards for gaming consoles and cloud-based platforms, encouraging companies to adopt greener technology.

b. Facilitating Industry Collaboration

Recommendation: Policymakers should foster partnerships between gaming companies, environmental organizations, and energy providers to promote mutual sustainability goals.

- **Action Point:** Establish cross-sector working groups to identify opportunities for gaming companies to adopt renewable energy solutions and reduce the environmental impact of their operations.

Recommendation: Collaborate with the gaming industry to collect and analyze data on player behaviors related to sustainability. This data can inform future policy decisions and create a feedback loop that enhances the effectiveness of climate-focused gaming content.

- **Action Point:** Develop public-private partnerships focused on sharing data insights that demonstrate the impact of gaming on player behavior and climate outcomes.

3. Environmental Organizations and Sustainability Advocates

a. Leveraging Gaming for Climate Action

Recommendation: Partner with game developers to create and promote in-game events, challenges, and missions that raise awareness about climate change and environmental conservation.

- **Action Point:** Work with gaming companies to sponsor sustainability challenges, encouraging players to participate in climate-positive actions like reforestation, clean-ups, and energy-saving behaviors, both in-game and in real life.

Recommendation: Use gaming platforms as tools for environmental education by embedding eco-friendly narratives within popular games.

- **Action Point:** Partner with educational institutions and gaming companies to create curriculum-based games or game-based learning modules that teach sustainability concepts to young players.

b. Enhancing Data Collection for Impact Measurement

Recommendation: Collaborate with game developers and policymakers to collect scientifically valid data on the effectiveness of sustainability efforts within games. Use this data to refine strategies and demonstrate the impact of gaming on real-world environmental actions.

- **Action Point:** Advocate for standardized data collection frameworks across the gaming industry that track and measure sustainability-related player actions and outcomes.

4. Gaming Communities and Influencers

a. Amplifying Sustainability Efforts

Recommendation: Gaming influencers and community leaders should use their platforms to promote sustainability messages, raising awareness about the environmental impact of gaming and the potential for games to drive positive change.

- **Action Point:** Leverage social media, streaming platforms, and in-game communities to highlight games that incorporate sustainability themes and encourage players to take part in eco-friendly gaming initiatives.

b. Supporting Green Game Initiatives

Recommendation: Gamers should advocate for energy-efficient gaming systems, games with sustainability themes, and more eco-conscious gaming habits.

- **Action Point:** Organize grassroots campaigns within the gaming community to demand more sustainable practices from developers, publishers, and platform holders.

Recommendation: Encourage peer-to-peer advocacy within gaming communities, building support for sustainability initiatives and influencing broader industry trends as well as climate policy.

- **Action Point:** Use community-driven challenges and competitions to inspire collective action toward environmental goals, fostering a sense of responsibility and collaboration.

Conclusion

The *Gaming for Good* roundtable highlighted the immense potential of the gaming industry to drive sustainability forward. By integrating climate-conscious themes into game design, fostering collaboration between stakeholders, and leveraging the power of the gaming community, the industry can become a vital platform for climate advocacy and action. The recom-

mendations outlined in this whitepaper provide a roadmap for the gaming industry, policy-makers, environmental organizations, and players to collectively unlock the power of gaming for a more sustainable future. Through innovation, collaboration, and a shared commitment to climate action, the gaming industry can play a transformative role in addressing one of the most critical challenges of our time.

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- Playing for the Planet Alliance Reports
- Industry Data on Gaming and Climate

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GREAT Overview

GREAT is an international research and innovation project that explores the potential impact of game-based approaches towards social engagement and the creation of new forms of dialogue between citizens and policy stakeholders. The project carries out a series of case studies in the context of climate emergency to test the innovative potential of games, offering citizens a means to express their preferences and attitudes on climate policy issues.

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An aerial photograph of a modern building complex featuring extensive green roofs and courtyards. The building has a mix of brick and metal facades. The courtyards are lush with greenery, including trees and shrubs. A paved area in the foreground shows two people walking. The overall scene is bright and green, suggesting a sustainable urban environment.

Rooftops Re-imagined

**GREEN ROOFS CYPRUS
INSIGHT REPORT 2025**

Dr Anna Merry and Dr Aravella Zachariou
Frederick University Cyprus

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Find out more:

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ROOFTOPS REIMAGINED:

GREEN ROOFS CYPRUS
INSIGHT REPORT 2025

Dr Anna Merry and Dr Aravella Zachariou
Frederick University Cyprus

“ We need to make the urban landscape more green, and rooftops offer a huge untapped opportunity to bring nature back into our cities.

- RICHARD ROGERS, ARCHITECT AND URBAN PLANNER

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“ A building should give back the space it takes up on the ground by replacing it with a garden in the sky.

-LE CORBUSIER

INTRODUCTION:

This insight report explores citizen perspectives towards a green roof policy in Cyprus. Green roofs provide energy efficiency, support biodiversity, improve air quality, and support climate resilience, yet, their adoption faces obstacles, including policy gaps, limited financial incentives, and low public awareness.

A recent case study, co-designed by Frederick University and the Urban Gorillas NGO through the GREAT project (Games Realizing Effective and Affective Transformation), co-funded by the EU's Horizon Programme and UKRI, utilized an interactive game to gather community input on approaches to green roofs and proposes strategies for policy makers. This report offers evidence-based recommendations to guide policymakers, urban planners, and stakeholders in promoting green roof initiatives

Can games impact climate change?

Three hour session dedicated to architects

The case study highlights how games can serve as a valuable bridge between public aspirations and policymaking, creating a foundation for long-term, inclusive urban planning in response to the climate crisis.

Three hour session dedicated to citizens

BACKGROUND:

Can games impact climate change?

To achieve carbon neutrality by 2050, it is essential to foster active collaboration between citizens and policymakers in embracing sustainable urban solutions.

Developed by Frederick University and case study sponsor Urban Gorillas NGO, the approach leverages the power of digital gaming to explore the potential of urban rooftops transforming into green, climate-resilient spaces, the method enhances both awareness and public engagement.

The GREAT initiative positions games as effective tools for engaging citizens in policy-related activities. Within the green roof case study, the use of a “serious dilemma game”¹ is utilized to engage citizens and stakeholders in simulation scenarios surrounding green rooftop projects. This approach allows participants to engage in the benefits of green roofs as well as exploring incentive structures to overcome common barriers.

Urban Gorillas, a member of the European Creative Rooftop Network Foundation, identified the complexities of rooftop utilization as a policy area, which led to the creation of a “serious dilemma game.” The game fosters role-playing and problem-solving, giving participants a realistic view of the challenges and advantages involved in implementing green roofs as a climate solution.

In Cyprus, this initiative draws on both local and international insights, including the first green roof pilot on a mixed-use building established by the Cyprus Energy Agency. This rooftop project set a precedent, illustrating the potential for widespread green roof adoption across urban centers like Nicosia. Through face-to-face game sessions, the project enables citizens to voice their opinions and learn through the benefits of such an initiative.

The format facilitates two-way knowledge transfer, allowing citizens to better understand sustainable initiatives and the potential for policymakers to gain insights into public perspectives.

Five in depth 3-hour sessions have been held, including three with a diverse range of citizens, one dedicated to architects, and one dedicated to Urban Planning Students in their final year of studies, revealing the game’s effectiveness in promoting sustainable urban planning practices. Feedback from participants indicates that these sessions have deepened their understanding of green roofs’ social and environmental impact, and enhanced their openness to green initiatives. Ultimately, the case study highlights how games can serve as a valuable bridge between public aspirations and policymaking, creating a foundation for long-term, inclusive urban planning in response to the climate crisis.

¹ A tool to immerse players in complex, real-world scenarios that require critical thinking and decision-making, helping them understand multifaceted issues more deeply.

Collaboration with the Cyprus Energy Agency for the European Climate Pact

Participants included Academics, Urban Planners, Members of the Cyprus Energy Agency, Design and Urban Planning students, Members of the Nicosia Municipality and Ministry of Agriculture.

Dissemination event on the Cyprus Energy Agency green rooftop: Taking the case study almost full circle, the event gathered together over 30 participants on the green roof which inspired the 'Rooftop Revolution Case Study'. During the event case study results were discussed and participants were able to play a shortened version of the DiBL game.

GREEN ROOFS DILEMMA GAME:

Rooftops Reimagined

Built on the 'DiBL' platform developed by Serious Games Interactive², "Rooftops Reimagined" is a multiplayer facilitator driven game which is designed to enable in-depth discussion and exploration. The game is divided into two parts.

PART 1

This presents the benefits of green rooftops, introduces various stakeholder perspectives –such as building managers, residents, and investors—and outlines challenges like safety, maintenance, and costs. Participants are also invited to propose and discuss incentives to overcome these barriers, considering the fairness of these incentives.

PART 2

Participants are assigned roles that differ from their own real-life positions, allowing them to explore viewpoints from different stakeholder perspectives. They debate, negotiate, and vote on policy incentives to achieve a fair consensus. A second dilemma round further develops this perspective-shifting approach, enhancing empathy and cooperative problem-solving.

Throughout gameplay, participants balance personal views with their assigned roles, debating and advocating for incentives they believe will be most effective. This structure encourages mutual understanding, demonstrating how inclusive incentives can drive successful projects centering around green infrastructure.

² DIBL. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://dibl.eu/> (Accessed 10 September 2023)

FINDINGS:

Benefits of Rooftop Utilisation

During the game sessions, participants identified an array of personal, environmental, and community benefits associated with green rooftop utilisation, revealing multifaceted advantages. Environmentally, green rooftops were valued for their ability to improve air quality and regulate climate. Participants also highlighted the sustainability benefits, noting how green rooftops naturally lower energy consumption in summer.

Socially, green rooftops were viewed as creating inviting spaces for community interaction and personal well-being. Many participants saw these rooftops as natural gathering spots where residents could socialize and foster stronger community bonds. They were also seen as peaceful, accessible locations for relaxation, offering views and a reconnection with nature. Additionally, participants valued the potential extra recreational space for activities like yoga, outdoor relaxation, or simply enjoying the city skyline, adding a sense of openness in crowded urban settings.

Lastly, green rooftops were seen to offer critical ecological benefits, supporting biodiversity by creating habitats for insects and bees, thus enriching urban ecosystems. They were viewed as spaces which could increase green spaces in cities, making them accessible to those without private outdoor areas and contributing to local biodiversity and sustainability efforts.

STATISTICS:

- Environmental and Climate
- Social and Recreational
- Urban Farming/ Food Production
- Functional and Practical
- Wellbeing
- Ecological and Biodiversity
- Aesthetic

Most Important **Challenges** to Rooftop Utilisation

- Maintenance and Upkeep
- Tenant Engagement/Cooperation
- Financial Constraints
- Safety Concerns
- Accessibility and Safety Concerns
- Child-Friendly Design
- Lack of Personal Space/ Privacy
- Design and Aesthetic Preferences

- Financial/ Cost-Related
- Community and Social Engagement
- Education and Awareness
- Safety and Protection
- Challenges and Feasibility

Stakeholder Engagement

Throughout the game, participants were invited through an anonymous vote, to choose which stakeholder in a green roof scenario they wanted to engage with first. The voting process highlighted distinct stakeholder priorities, illuminating the perceived importance of each group in the context of green roof initiatives.

In the first round, 64% of participants opted to speak with the “building manager,” reasoning that the manager, as the individual responsible for building operations, would play a key role in rooftop implementation. This choice underscores the building manager’s influence and the need for a strong management role in building operations. Urban planners in later interviews also noted that current building management in Cyprus is underdeveloped and awaits legislative support, which would facilitate such green initiatives.

In the second voting round, 69% of participants selected the “Top Floor Young Couple,” who had expressed a desire to own part of the roof. Participants reasoned that, given their proximity and vested interest, this couple would be among the most impacted by rooftop changes.

Finally, in the third round, 66% of participants chose to engage with “Parents with Children,” identifying them as another group with specific needs related to rooftop space use. Notably, “Senior Citizens” did not secure enough votes in any session, suggesting that their perspectives were perceived as less directly impacted or adequately understood by participants. However, feedback from focus groups suggested that participants already recognized the unique challenges faced by older residents in such settings.

This sequence of preferences highlights participants’ focus on stakeholders with active or vested interests in rooftop utilization, revealing the priority placed on those who would either manage or directly benefit from green roof initiatives.

Barriers to Rooftop Utilisation

After engaging with stakeholders, participants identified several pressing barriers to rooftop utilization, with safety, long-term sustainability, and maintenance being the top concerns. These issues reflect a strong focus on ensuring that rooftop spaces are both secure and durable over time. Financial constraints also emerged as a critical barrier, underscoring concerns about the economic feasibility of implementing such projects.

The barriers identified spanned several domains—financial, technical, social, and environmental. Economically, high initial costs, ongoing maintenance expenses, and limited financial support were seen as major challenges. These concerns highlight the need for effective funding mechanisms and incentives to make rooftop greening more accessible, especially for older buildings. In terms of technical and structural issues, participants emphasized the importance of proper planning, including the use of high-quality waterproofing materials and drainage systems to prevent water leakage and structural damage. Additionally, the perceived level of workmanship, particularly in Cyprus, was identified as a significant concern.

Climate considerations were also a key focus, particularly the harsh Cypriot sun. Participants recommended using drought-resistant plants and efficient irrigation systems to maintain green roofs

during the long, hot summer months. They also raised concerns about the environmental impact of water usage for rooftop gardens, although solutions like utilizing water lost from air conditioning units were suggested.

Socially, the creation of communal rooftop spaces was seen positively for fostering community interaction and providing recreational areas. However, concerns about privacy for top-floor residents and the need for child-friendly designs also emerged. Disagreements over rooftop management in multi-tenant buildings were identified as another potential obstacle.

The barriers to rooftop utilization identified during the game sessions were multifaceted, with significant challenges across financial, technical, social, and environmental domains.

On the environmental side, participants pointed to challenges related to climate suitability, water availability, pest control, and air quality. Additionally, concerns about “greenwashing” were raised, with some participants suggesting alternative green infrastructure solutions, such as planting more trees along streets and creating walkable green spaces, to achieve urban greening without the complexity of rooftop gardens.

The barriers to rooftop utilization identified during the game sessions were multifaceted, with significant challenges across financial, technical, social, and environmental domains. Addressing these issues requires a holistic approach that includes effective funding, technical expertise, careful climate considerations, and community-focused planning.

POLICY INSIGHTS:

Suggestions for Advancing Green Rooftop Utilization

The following insights have emerged as key considerations for successfully implementing a green rooftop policy. These suggestions are designed to inform and guide the development of policies and incentives that will foster the adoption of green rooftops. They emphasize the need for flexible, inclusive, and sustainable approaches to integrating green rooftops into urban environments.

Establish Clear Communication Frameworks

Policymakers should mandate the creation of structured communication channels between residents, building managers, and property owners. This will ensure collaborative planning and prevent cost increases linked to maintenance needs and operational challenges of green rooftops.

Ensure Equity and Transparency in Incentive Structures

Develop and enforce guidelines for incentives that ensure fairness in the distribution of benefits. Policies should prevent misuse by establishing clear and transparent criteria to guarantee that all stakeholders, including economically disadvantaged residents, have access to the benefits of rooftop greening.

Incentivize Long-Term Sustainability

Incentive programs should be structured to reward long-term commitment to sustainability. Policies should prioritize green roofs that offer lasting environmental and economic benefits, ensuring that such projects continue to support climate resilience and energy efficiency over time.

Provide Financial Support for Disadvantaged Residents

Implement financial mechanisms, such as subsidies, rent discounts, or reductions in common expenses, to make green rooftops more accessible to low-income residents. This will ensure that rooftop greening initiatives are inclusive and do not exacerbate existing social inequalities.

Support Market Differentiation

Through Green Certifications Encourage property owners to invest in green rooftop solutions by offering incentives for obtaining 'green building' certifications. These certifications should be linked to increased property value, making sustainable building practices more appealing to investors and developers.

Invest in Skill Development and Capacity Building

Policymakers should allocate resources for targeted training and skill development programs for building managers, architects, developers, and other relevant stakeholders. This will ensure that those responsible for green roof implementation have the necessary expertise to execute and maintain these systems effectively.

Adopt Flexible Policies for Varied Building Types

Recognize the diversity of building types and economic contexts by adopting flexible policies that accommodate the unique needs of older buildings and properties with different financial capabilities. This approach will allow green rooftop projects to be scaled and adapted to a variety of urban settings.

Provide Evidence and Data

Policymakers should ensure that architects, developers, and property owners have access to comprehensive data on the benefits and costs of green roofs. Providing quantitative evidence on energy savings, environmental benefits, and cost reductions will facilitate informed decision-making and encourage wider adoption.

Extended Warranty Periods for Green Roof Installations

Policies should incentivize green roof installations by offering extended warranty periods. This reduces the perceived risk for property owners and makes green roofs a more attractive investment by ensuring long-term durability and performance.

Implement Clear Resident Agreements

Establish policies that require residents to enter into formal agreements regarding the responsibilities and benefits of maintaining green roofs, similar to those for photovoltaic (PV) panel installations. This will clarify expectations and encourage greater resident participation in rooftop projects.

Anticipate Diverse Developer Responses

To foster collaboration and support, it is essential to emphasize the potential advantages of green roofs, including increased property value, enhanced corporate social responsibility (CSR) opportunities, and marketing benefits that developers can leverage to strengthen their portfolios and appeal to eco-conscious consumers.

These policy insights outline actionable steps for local and national governments to promote the widespread adoption of green rooftops.

The key focus areas include incentivizing sustainability, providing financial support for disadvantaged residents, ensuring fair and transparent policies, and supporting education and training for all involved stakeholders. By addressing the technical, social, and financial barriers to green roof implementation, policymakers can significantly advance the environmental and economic benefits of green rooftops while fostering social inclusion.

The “Rooftops Reimagined” initiative in Cyprus has provided an innovative platform for urban planning consultation, bridging the gap between citizens and policymakers on the complex issue of green rooftops. Using the GREAT approach and interactive gaming techniques, this initiative enabled diverse stakeholders to engage in meaningful discussions and explore solutions to the challenges and opportunities of rooftop utilization.

CONCLUSION:

Bridging the Gap for a Sustainable Future

The findings from the initiative reveal a set of pressing challenges and opportunities for green rooftop implementation, spanning financial, technical, social, and environmental domains. Financial constraints emerged as a key barrier, particularly the high initial costs, ongoing maintenance, and lack of financial support. Participants emphasized the need for targeted incentives, subsidies, and effective funding mechanisms to make rooftop greening projects accessible to a broader range of buildings and residents.

On the technical front, the importance of high-quality planning and materials was stressed, especially regarding waterproofing, drainage, and structural integrity. Given Cyprus' climate challenges, participants suggested solutions such as drought-resistant plants and efficient irrigation systems to ensure the long-term sustainability of green rooftops. Furthermore, climate suitability and the availability of water were identified as critical environmental concerns that must be addressed for green roofs to thrive.

Socially, the initiative highlighted the need for greater community engagement, particularly in multi-tenant buildings. While shared rooftop spaces were seen as valuable for fostering community interaction, participants noted privacy concerns and the importance of designing child-friendly spaces. Collaborative decision-making among

residents, building managers, and developers emerged as a necessary condition for successful rooftop projects, particularly in navigating shared-space etiquette and addressing accessibility concerns.

The environmental benefits of green rooftops, such as improved air quality, reduced heat island effects, and increased biodiversity, were widely recognized. However, participants stressed the importance of strategic implementation to maximize these benefits, particularly in areas with climate and water challenges. The project also revealed that green rooftops could enhance the value of properties, contribute to corporate social responsibility (CSR) goals, and offer significant community benefits, especially when applied to public buildings.

By integrating diverse perspectives and adopting an innovative, game-based consultation model, "Rooftops Reimagined" has demonstrated the power of inclusive planning processes to address complex urban issues. The insights gathered from this initiative serve as a roadmap for policymakers, developers, and urban planners to create more sustainable, community-driven solutions for green rooftops. Moving forward, these findings should inform the development of policies, incentives, and best practices that not only overcome the barriers to rooftop greening but also encourage its wider adoption in urban environments.

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Klimajobs für eine nachhaltige Zukunft

Ergänzende Zusammenfassung

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ECKDATEN

Schulen: 10 Schulklassen (9 Schulen)

Schulstandorte: 3 im ländlichen Bereich, 6 in Wien und Umgebung;

Datum der Durchführung des Dilemma Spiels: April – Juni 2024

Anzahl der Schüler:innen: 191 Personen

Alter: 15+

ZUSAMMEFASSUNG DER ANALYSE

Basierend auf den Anmerkungen und Ergänzungen während der Diskussionen lässt sich Folgendes ergänzen:

1. Motivation bei der Berufswahl

Die Schüler:innen nannten mehrere Schlüssel motivatoren für ihre Berufswahl:

- **Finanzielle Aspekte:** Mehrere Schüler:innen betonten die Wichtigkeit des Einkommens. Es wurde häufig erwähnt, dass die Möglichkeit, viel Geld zu verdienen, eine zentrale Rolle spielt.
- **Interessen und Erfüllung:** Freude an der Arbeit und die Übereinstimmung mit persönlichen Interessen wurden ebenfalls hervorgehoben.
- **Work-Life-Balance und Flexibilität:** Die Notwendigkeit von flexiblen Arbeitszeiten wurde als wichtig erachtet, um die Vereinbarkeit von Beruf und Freizeit zu gewährleisten.
- **Sicherheit und Zukunftsperspektiven:** Die Schüler:innen streben nach sicheren Berufen mit guten Zukunftsaussichten.

2. Maßnahmen zur Begeisterung für Klimajobs

In den Diskussionen wurden zahlreiche ergänzende Vorschläge und Anmerkungen zu den Maßnahmen geäußert:

- **Praktika und Schnuppertage:** Es wurde betont, dass Pflichtpraktika in Klimajobs nicht nur stattfinden sollten, sondern auch gut bezahlt werden müssten. Die Schüler:innen sollten aus einem Pool von Klimajobs wählen können.
- **Öffentlichkeitsarbeit:** Die Werbung in der Öffentlichkeit sollte zeitgemäße (soziale) Medien wie TikTok nutzen, um Jugendliche direkt anzusprechen. Zudem wurde die Notwendigkeit betont, dass die Werbung positiv gestaltet sein sollte, da negative Bilder (bspw. zu den zerstörerischen Auswirkungen des Klimawandels) nicht gut ankommen.
- **Finanzielle Anreize:** Staatliche Subventionen könnten Anreize bieten, sich für Klimajobs zu entscheiden. Vorschläge wie Steuerboni für Klimajobs, sowie die Einführung eines kostenlosen ÖPNV-Tickets oder eines "Klimapasses" für Beschäftigte in diesem Bereich wurden als Anreiz diskutiert.
- **Einführung von Klimaschutz als Schulfach:** Einige Schüler:innen äußerten Bedenken, dass sie nicht gezwungen werden möchten, Klimaschutz als Fach

zu wählen. Dies zeigt, dass Freiwilligkeit bei der Entscheidung für Klimajobs gewünscht wird.

3. Kommunikationsstrategien für Geschlechtervielfalt in Klimajobs

Die Schüler:innen erarbeiteten mehrere Ansätze, um mehr junge Frauen und nicht-binäre Personen für Klimajobs zu gewinnen:

- **Repräsentation und Vorbilder:** Die Wichtigkeit von Vorbildern in der Werbung und bei Veranstaltungen wurde betont. Frauen und nicht-binäre Personen in Klimajobs sollten sichtbar gemacht werden, um positive „Role Models“ zu schaffen.
- **Gleichberechtigung in der Bezahlung:** Es wurde darauf hingewiesen, dass das Thema Bezahlung nicht nur für Frauen, sondern für alle Geschlechter gleich behandelt werden sollte. Jede:r sollte das gleiche Gehalt erhalten.
- **Stereotypen abbauen:** Die Schüler:innen forderten, dass stereotype Geschlechterrollen schon im Kindesalter vermieden werden sollten. Dies könnte durch Aufklärung und spezielle Programme in Schulen erreicht werden.
- **Kreative Programme:** Vorschläge für spezielle Veranstaltungen wie den „Girls Day“ wurden gemacht, um junge Frauen und nicht-binäre Personen anzusprechen und einzubeziehen. Diese könnten auch personalisiert sein oder bei speziellen Events, wie dem Frauenlauf oder bei der Pride Parade stattfinden.

4. Anmerkungen und Ergänzungen zu den Diskussionen

Die Reflexion der Schüler:innen während der Diskussionen brachte wichtige zusätzliche Erkenntnisse:

- **Stärkung des gesellschaftlichen Stellenwerts von Klimajobs:** Ein zentraler Punkt in den Diskussionen war die Notwendigkeit, den gesellschaftlichen Wert von Klimajobs klar zu kommunizieren und zu stärken. Die Schüler:innen betonten, dass Klimajobs nicht nur als Berufe, sondern als wichtige Beiträge zur Bekämpfung des Klimawandels und zur Förderung einer nachhaltigen Zukunft wahrgenommen werden sollten. Um das Bewusstsein für die Bedeutung dieser Berufe zu schärfen, sollten Aufklärungskampagnen entwickelt werden, die die positiven Auswirkungen von Klimajobs auf die Umwelt und die

Gesellschaft hervorheben. Durch die Sichtbarmachung von Erfolgsgeschichten und positiven Beispielen aus der Praxis könnten Jugendliche motiviert werden, sich in diesen Bereichen zu engagieren. Zudem könnte die Förderung von Klimajobs als gesellschaftlicher Wert in den Medien und der öffentlichen Diskussion helfen, diese Berufe attraktiver zu gestalten und das Interesse an ihnen zu steigern.

- **Erfahrung und Realität:** Die Schüler:innen waren sich bewusst, dass Klimajobs viele Möglichkeiten bieten, aber sie forderten auch realistische Darstellungen dieser Berufe, um potenzielle Missverständnisse zu vermeiden.
- **Interesse an Klimajobs:** Während viele Schüler:innen grundsätzlich offen für Klimajobs waren, äußerten sie auch das Bedürfnis, mehr über andere Berufsfelder zu erfahren. Ein gewisses Desinteresse oder Unentschlossenheit wurde deutlich, da einige alternative Karrierewege in Betracht zogen.
- **Vorbereitung und Rollenverständnis für das Dilemma Spiel:** Einige Schüler:innen wünschten sich mehr Vorbereitung auf die Themen und eine Möglichkeit, verschiedene Rollen in den Diskussionen einzunehmen. Dies könnte die Dynamik und die Tiefe der Diskussionen verbessern.

Fazit

Die spielerischen Interventionen zeigen, dass finanzielle Sicherheit, persönliche Interessen und Flexibilität zentrale Motivationsfaktoren für Jugendliche sind. Die Anmerkungen und Ergänzungen zu den Diskussionen unterstreichen die Bedeutung von positiven Darstellungen, Freiwilligkeit bei der Wahl von Klimajobs und die Notwendigkeit, Stereotypen zu überwinden.

Die Schüler:innen sind offen für kreative Ansätze und schätzen die Möglichkeit, in Diskussionen unterschiedliche Perspektiven einzunehmen. Diese Einsichten könnten dazu beitragen, spezifische Programme und Kommunikationsstrategien zu entwickeln, um Jugendliche für Klimajobs zu begeistern und Geschlechtervielfalt zu fördern.

Bildquelle: Barbara Kieslinger 2024

Policy Insight Briefing

Executive Summary

This brief from the GREAT project, provides policy recommendations drawing on contributions from policymakers, academics, game developers, UN agencies, investors, and civil society organisations at a recent workshop held in New York. The paper outlines how games function as a powerful infrastructure for policy dialogue, citizen engagement and voice, climate action, and systemic change.

Introduction

The GREAT (Games Realising Effective & Affective Transformation) Project explores the potential of games to foster social engagement and enhance dialogue between citizens and policymakers. A programme of practical case studies is underway, fostering citizen engagement and in the democratic process, with a focus on climate change policy priorities. Games culture is ubiquitous, and games are now this preeminent entertainment media globally, but their potential for interaction between citizens and policymakers has not yet been explored. The GREAT case studies leverage innovative engagement strategies to investigate how games-based activities can enable citizens to express their views on social and policy dilemmas. This initiative is supported by UK Research and Innovation and the EU's Horizon Europe program..

Methods

GREAT deploys technologies and methodologies that create new communication channels between citizens and policymakers, generating actionable insights for policy makers while respecting ethics and data privacy. This is achieved through co-designed, scalable interventions tested in real-world conditions, engaging audiences that can be difficult to reach using more established methodologies. Two principal approaches are investigated: Firstly, dilemma-based serious games are used to generate in-depth qualitative insights from a relatively small, moderated group of participants. Secondly, questions for players are embedded in high profile games, enabling quantitative data to be obtained from very large numbers of respondents, who can be engaged at global, national or district level. Throughout the project, we employ participatory methods, involving key audiences, including policy stakeholders, in the design, prototyping, and research phases. Authentic input, interaction, and collaboration are crucial, with continuous feedback and optimization. With our citizen science approach, we go beyond mere consultation, uncovering implicit knowledge through varying degrees of participation, from consultation to empowerment. While the focus of GREAT is on the global challenges of sustainability and climate change the project methodologies are both scalable and transferable to other issues.

Games can function as:

- A bridge between citizens and institutions at a time of declining trust in traditional political processes.
- A parallel public sphere where dialogue can occur across geopolitical boundaries.
- A scalable engagement mechanism capable of reaching millions of players in ways that conventional consultations cannot.
- Effectively facilitate a two-way dialogue, listening to players, understanding sentiment to produce actionable insights.

Games and Policy Dialogue: From Voice to Impact

Giving Players a Voice

A central theme was the demonstrated willingness of players to engage with societal issues when approached respectfully and non-intrusively. Experiences discussed during the workshop indicated:

- Short, well-integrated in-game prompts can achieve high engagement and completion rates.
- Players respond positively when participation is framed as having a voice as opposed to being 'taught' or 'persuaded'.
- Large-scale engagement can generate globally comparable data on attitudes toward climate, sustainability, and governance.

The Policy Challenge: What Happens After Data Collection?

While data collection at scale is achievable, participants highlighted a gap between citizen input and policy outcomes. Key challenges identified include:

- Policy focus: Define a clearly articulated policy objective before engaging players at scale
- Translation: Policymakers may lack the data literacy or frameworks needed to interpret player-generated insights.
- Feedback loops: Players rarely see how their input influences decisions, weakening long-term trust and engagement.

Toward Actionable Policy Pathways

The workshop identified pathways to strengthen the link between games and policy impact:

- Align game-based consultations with formal policy mechanisms (e.g. parliamentary petitions, national consultations).
- Partner with policy intermediaries who understand legislative and regulatory processes.
- Use smaller, facilitated dilemma-based games to define priorities, followed by large-scale in-game engagement.
- Treating policy engagement as an iterative dialogue rather than consultation.

In-Game Activations: Awareness, Behaviour, and Hope

Design for Engagement, Not Overload

Participants emphasised that climate-related content must be carefully designed to avoid fatigue or disengagement, particularly among younger audiences. Effective approaches should:

- Integrate sustainability into existing mechanics (intrinsic) rather than adding external (extrinsic) messaging.
- Use accessible language (e.g. “nature” rather than politicised terminology).
- Offer agency and choice over prescriptive instruction.
- Be conscious of potential survey fatigue amongst players

Behaviour Change and Real-World Action

Evidence shared during the workshop indicated:

- In-game experiences can prompt real-world actions when players feel empowered rather than judged.
- Collective events and time-bound activations can amplify impact.
- Players often want to do more but lack clear guidance on what actions matter.

Games can act as navigational tools, helping players move from concern to action.

Extended Realities (XR), Empathy, and the Next Frontier

Extended reality (XR) technologies were highlighted as a powerful next step, specifically:

- Build empathy through embodied experience.
- Make global or abstract issues feel personal.
- Support measurable shifts in perception and understanding.

XR was framed not as a replacement for games, but as a complementary medium that expands the engagement toolkit.

Cross-Cutting Themes and Key Insights

The workshop identified several unifying themes:

- Dialogue over didacticism: Listening is as important as informing.
- Focus and clarity: Impact requires targeted policy goals and clear success metrics.
- Hope and agency: Especially for younger audiences, solutions must accompany problems.
- Collaboration: Meaningful change depends on partnerships across industry, academia, policy, and civil society.
- Scalability with care: Large reach must be balanced with respect for player experience and not disrupt player 'flow'.

Insights for policy dialogue

Games are emerging as authentic critical infrastructures for engagement, dialogue, and transformation. The challenge ahead is how intentionally and collaboratively this potential is realised. In aligning player voice, industry innovation, and policy priorities, the GREAT project and its partners can help turn play into participation, data into dialogue, and engagement into impact.

Summary Recommendations

- **1. Define policy objectives early** and co-design game-based interventions with policymakers.
- **2. Embed player voice mechanisms** directly into games in non-intrusive, time-efficient ways.
- **3. Develop feedback loops** that show participants how their input influences outcomes.
- **4. Prioritise systems-level decarbonisation**, focusing on efficiency gains with co-benefits.
- **5. Invest in creative integration**, ensuring sustainability content aligns with gameplay and player motivation.
- **6. Support research and measurement**, including longitudinal studies of behaviour and attitude change.
- **7. Frame sustainability with hope**, highlighting achievable actions and collective progress.

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Further information

Partners

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Frederick University, Cyprus

University of Bolton, England

Sphaira Innovation Ltd (PlanetPlay), England

Associate Partners

Northwest University, South Africa

Beijing Normal University, China

Project details	Publications
https://www.greatproject.gg/	https://zenodo.org/communities/101094766/

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